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A Biblical View on Disability

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Abstract

This short article explores the meaning of disability through both a contemporary and biblical lens. It begins by defining disability as a multifaceted interaction between health conditions and social or environmental barriers, referencing the framework presented by the World Health Organization (WHO). The discussion then shifts to the biblical portrayal of individuals with disabilities, emphasizing themes such as human dignity, compassion, divine purpose, and ultimate restoration. While the Holy Bible does not use modern terminology, it affirms the value of all people, showing that disability neither diminishes worth nor precludes inclusion in God's redemptive work. Through scriptural analysis, the article highlights how disability is integrated into the broader narrative of human experience, theological meaning, and hope.

Keywords: *Disability, Divine Purpose, Holy Bible, Human Dignity, Inclusion*

1. Meaning of Disability

The term 'disability' generally refers to a condition (i.e., physical, cognitive, sensory, mental health-related, or developmental) that substantially limits one or more major life activities. According to the World Health Organization (2011), disability results from the interaction between individuals with a health condition and personal and environmental barriers that hinder their full and effective participation in society. It is not only about an individual's impairment but also about the social and structural limitations placed upon them.

The Holy Bible and Disability

The Holy Bible does not use the modern word 'disability,' but it does describe people with physical, sensory, behavioral (conative), emotional (affective), or cognitive (intellectual) differences. The biblical perspective can be summarized into several themes with respective examples to illustrate each of them:

(1) Disability as Part of the Human Condition

Disability is acknowledged as part of life in a broken world but not as something that diminishes a person's worth. For instance, in the book of Leviticus, the following verse says: "You shall not curse the deaf or put a stumbling block before the blind, but you shall fear your God: I am the Lord" (Leviticus 19:14, ESV; Crossway, 2001). This verse highlights respect, dignity, and protection for people with disabilities.

(2) Compassion and Inclusion

Jesus consistently showed compassion toward people with disabilities and included them in His ministry. For example, Isaiah 35:5-6 (ESV) says, “Then the eyes of the blind shall be opened, and the ears of the deaf unstopped; then shall the lame man leap like a deer, and the tongue of the mute sing for joy.” This prophetic vision anticipates restoration and hope. In another example found in the Gospel according to Saint Matthew, it is recorded that “Jesus went throughout all the cities and villages ... healing every disease and every affliction” (Matthew 9:35, ESV; Crossway, 2001). In this instance, Jesus engaged directly with people experiencing disability, affirming their value and offering healing (Yong, 2011).

(3) Disability and the Image of God

The Holy Bible has taught that all people, regardless of ability, are made in the image of God: “So God created man in his own image, in the image of God he created him; male and female he created them” (Genesis 1:27, ESV; Crossway, 2001). This verse establishes human dignity and worth that disability does not erase. As Creamer (2009) emphasizes, theology that incorporates disability recognizes the sacredness of all embodied lives and reimagines limitations as part of God’s good creation.

(4) Disability and Divine Purpose

Disability is not seen as punishment, but sometimes as an opportunity to reveal God’s work. For example, in the Gospel according to Saint John 9:2-3, when asked about a man born blind, “Jesus answered, ‘It was not that this man sinned, or his parents, but that the works of God might be displayed in him’” (ESV; Crossway, 2001). Here, the term ‘disability’ is reframed as a context for God’s power and presence to be revealed (Yong, 2011).

(5) Future Hope and Restoration

The Holy Bible points to a future where disability and suffering will be overcome. As mentioned in the last book of the scripture, The Revelation of the Apostle Saint John, it is stated that “He will wipe away every tear from their eyes, and death shall be no more, neither shall there be mourning, nor crying, nor pain anymore” (Revelation 21:4, ESV; Crossway, 2001). This is a vision of ultimate healing and inclusion in God’s kingdom (Creamer, 2009).

Conclusion

Both contemporary and biblical perspectives affirm that disability should not be viewed solely as an individual deficit, but rather as a complex interplay between personal differences and broader societal or environmental factors (WHO, 2011). The Holy Bible, while using different language than modern discourse, consistently upholds the dignity, value, and purpose of individuals with disabilities. Through its teachings on compassion, inclusion, divine image, and future restoration, the holy scripture challenges the stigma of disability and promotes a vision of a just and inclusive community (Yong, 2011; Creamer, 2009). Disability, therefore, is not, or should not be, a mark of exclusion, but a meaningful aspect of human diversity through which God’s presence, power, and promises are made known.

References

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